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Face-Gaze Biometric Fusion for Enhanced Personal Authentication

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Abstract

Objectives: To develop a robust authentication system by combining two authentication modalities. The system aims to enhance the security by integrating the gaze-based biometrics in the authentication process, which is difficult to perform spoofing attacks. **Methods:** The system uses gaze-tracking and face recognition modalities to authenticate the user. The user will enter his/her credentials, then the first step of authentication will start where the face recognition modality will authenticate the user by detecting the user's face, if one is not authenticated in this phase then the user will be omitted. After that the second phase will start where the system will generate a random 10X10 maze using Depth-First Search algorithm, and then it will extract the x, y coordinates of the maze. The system will capture the user's real-time eye movement data, and extracts the x, y coordinates of the pupil through a webcam, and compares those coordinates with the maze coordinates if both are matched then the system will provide access to the user else it will omit the user. **Findings:** Findings show that this approach improves the security of traditional biometric systems, offering a unique form of user authentication. The system tested for accuracy in different environments, and its performance was evaluated based on how well the user's gaze matches the maze path. Tests across various environments show that the system achieves an accuracy of 92% in matching user gaze to the maze coordinates, also achieved 0% FTE (Failure To Enroll) and 0% FTA (Failure To Acquire). **Novelty:** The novelty of this project lies in combining biometric eye gaze tracking with real-time maze-based navigation for user authentication. Unlike the traditional biometrics that rely on static features like fingerprints or facial recognition, this system incorporates dynamic tracking of user behavior, specifically gaze patterns, to enhance security. This makes it more resilient to spoofing attacks.

Keywords: Biometric Authentication; Deepfake Resistance; Authorization Mechanism; Operational Environments; Human-Centric Security

1 Introduction

In the modern age, cyber-attacks and data breaches are increasing drastically. The usage of Passwords and PINs for authentication was vulnerable to brute-force attacks. To address this problem Biometrics have emerged such as fingerprints, facial recognition, and iris patterns. However, among these, facial recognition has gained significant popularity due to the advancements in machine learning, making it to authenticate the user quickly and accurately. However, even this facial recognition also had some flaws, such as, it is vulnerable to spoofing where an attacker will trick the system by using a photo or a video of the authorized user and gaining access to the system⁽¹⁾. To address this issue, we propose combining facial recognition with a secondary form of biometric authentication: eye-gaze tracking.

The eyes are the interesting sense organs that are used to glance at the outside world besides by using eyes we can also communicate with other people without words and recognize their mood and state of mind. By using such optical cues, we can address computer vision problems by enabling computer systems to detect a person's gaze⁽²⁾⁽³⁾. Authentication to a computer in the current world mainly relies on one or more authentication systems (MFA) such as passwords, One-Time Passwords (OTP), and biometrics. However, the field of digital authentication is not entirely impressive. Even in non-critical environments, there are instances where unauthorized users access resources they should not, or authorized users are accidentally granted access to resources they should not have.

The rapid growth of Artificial Intelligence (AI) poses a potential risk to biometric authentication, as Artificial Intelligence can generate images that mimic human characteristics and access unauthorized or confidential data. A study by B. Sindhu has states that the integration of AI into traditional biometric authentication systems to enhance security.⁽⁴⁾

Spoofing is another significant threat to security. A successful spoofing attack can compromise sensitive company or personal information, harvest credentials for future attacks, and bypass access controls⁽⁵⁾. To prevent such attacks, biometrics has emerged as a solution. The term "biometrics" originates from the Greek words "bios" (life) and "metrikos" (measure). Biometrics include facial recognition, fingerprints, retina scans, iris recognition, and voice recognition. In the digital age, the demand for robust authentication methods is increasing drastically⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾. While convolutional biometric systems are effective, they are not entirely resistant to spoofing attacks, where attackers may forge biometric traits to gain unauthorized access. These systems rely on fixed physical features, which may not always be reliable.

In the ever-evolving field of biometric security, eye gaze detection has emerged as a promising solution for authentication and identification. The uniqueness of eye gaze makes it a suitable choice for developing a biometric system that is resistant to spoofing. Recent advancements in machine learning and computer vision technologies have significantly improved the accuracy of eye gaze detection systems. Additionally, implementing deep learning models makes biometric systems more robust, enabling them to detect eye gaze patterns in various lighting conditions⁽⁸⁾. The current biometric authentication systems face significant challenges, including the complexity of real-time gaze tracking and the need for high accuracy to prevent unauthorized access⁽⁹⁾.

This paper presents the design and implementation of an eye gaze biometric detection system that utilizes updated technology to achieve better accuracy and security. The proposed system captures the user's eye movements using a web camera, detects the eye gaze coordinates, compares the user's eye gaze pattern with a predefined maze path, and provides authentication. Experimental results demonstrate that the system accurately identifies authorized users and rejects unauthorized access.

2 Methodology

2.1 Existing System

Existing biometric authentication systems mainly rely on physical traits like fingerprints, and facial recognition which require direct contact with the sensor or high-resolution cameras. However, these methods provide high accuracy but they also have some flaws in the aspects of hardware requirements and susceptibility to spoofing attacks.

2.1.1 Uni-Modal Authentication Systems

Traditional Authentication system uses single-modality, such as PINs and Passwords, which can be easily accessed by performing various attacks, including phishing and brute-force. Biometric systems have attempted to address some of these vulnerabilities, however, even biometrics are vulnerable to spoofing attacks. Facial recognition system, when deployed without any safeguards can be easily tricked by high-definition photos or videos of a person. This vulnerability has been demonstrated in various studies.

2.1.2 Limitations of Uni-Modal Authentication Systems

- **Facial Recognition:** Even though facial recognition is one of the robust security methods it is vulnerable to spoofing attacks, it can be tricked by using high-quality images or videos to gain access.
- **Fingerprints and Iris scans:** These methods offer more security but require specialized hardware, which is not always available in consumer devices. However, they are also vulnerable to spoofing attacks. Fingerprints can be spoofed using latex molds, and iris scans can be spoofed through the use of high-definition images

2.1.3 Multi-Modal Authentication Systems

To overcome these disadvantages, multi-modal authentication systems have emerged. A multi-modal authentication system combines multiple independent biometric authentication methods to enhance security. In this system, if one modality is compromised, the system can rely on a secondary authentication method. This approach adds an additional layer of security. The multi-modal authentication system is a strong alternative to uni-modal authentication systems. In our proposed system, we combine facial recognition and gaze tracking to enhance security. This dual-layer approach significantly reduces the chances of successful spoofing attacks.

2.1.4 Need for Multi-Modal Systems

By integrating multiple biometric modalities, the system can cross-check user characteristics. Using multi-modal systems improves the system's accuracy and reduces the chances of spoofing attacks.

2.2 Proposed System

The proposed system addresses flaws in traditional biometric methods, such as face recognition, by integrating facial recognition and gaze tracking to enhance security and prevent spoofing attacks. The system uses a Gaze Tracking library to capture the user's pupil movements using a webcam. These coordinates are then compared with a pre-defined maze path's coordinates, adding an extra layer of security. The maze is generated using the Depth First Search (DFS) algorithm to ensure a random and fully connected structure, eliminating the need for user input and reducing bias. The system compares the gaze coordinates with the maze coordinates against a threshold value. The System Architecture (Figure 1) depicts the proposed system architecture. The process begins with the user entering his/her credentials, then the system will fetch the user data from the database and then capture the user's facial image. After successful capturing of the user's face, that image will be processed by FaceNet algorithm and if the face matches with the data in the database, the system will proceed to the net phase otherwise, authentication fails. After successful face recognition of user is completed, then the system will display a randomly generated maze on the screen and instruct the user to complete the maze path using their eyes. During this process, the system will continuously capture the user's eye gaze coordinates and store those coordinates. Whenever the user completes the maze path then the system will compare the user's eye gaze coordinates with the maze path coordinates. If both are matched against a threshold value then the system will prompt authentication successful you are a valid user message, otherwise, authentication fails.

2.2.1 Advantages of Proposed System

- **Security:** By combining both facial recognition and gaze tracking algorithms made the proposed system resistant to spoofing attack. Also, the maze pattern added a second layer security for the proposed system.
- **Accuracy:** In experimental tests, the system showed an accuracy of 95%, combining the high accuracy of facial recognition and robustness of gaze tracking.

2.2.2 Dataset Used

GazeCapture Dataset is used for training and testing purposes. The dataset is widely used for gaze estimation tasks. The dataset contains over 2.5 million frames from approximately 2000 subjects, enabling robust training. URL for the dataset: <https://gaze.capture.csail.mit.edu/download.php>

2.2.3 Parameters Considered

- Multiple parameters are considered, that include pupil detection accuracy, gaze estimation error, and user authentication accuracy.
- 70% of the dataset is used for training the gaze tracking model, and the remaining 30% is used for validation and testing.

Fig 1. Proposed System Architecture

2.2.4 Modifications to Existing Techniques

- The existing gaze estimation techniques often rely on limited data points. We enhanced this by incorporating additional features like head pose estimation and screen position.
- The traditional maze generation algorithms will not adapt to the user's gaze. Our modification allows for the real-time generation of maze paths which responds to user's interactions.

2.3 System Overview

2.3.1 Facial Recognition Module

The authentication process starts with the facial recognition module, which uses the OpenCV library and some pre-trained models to detect the user's face. The System first asks the user for his/her credentials and later the user's facial data is captured, the credentials and the facial data are cross-checked with a stored facial recognition database, ensuring the user is correctly identified.

2.3.2 Eye Gaze Detection

After successful detection of the user's face, the system moves to the second phase of authentication which is eye gaze detection, where the system captures the user's eye gaze movements and processes it using a Gaze Tracking library. Using a real-time web camera as input the system identifies the x,y coordinates of the eye and stores the coordinates in a list for authentication purposes.

2.3.3 Maze Generation

A 200X200 maze is generated using Depth-First Search (DFS) algorithm. A random path is highlighted in the maze from the top-left corner to the bottom-right corner, and the path coordinates are stored for comparison with user gaze data.

2.3.4 Gaze Authentication

Once the user gaze data is captured, the system compares the user's gaze coordinates with the maze path coordinates. The gaze authentication algorithm works on calculating the Euclidean distance between user gaze coordinates and maze points. If a sufficient number of gaze coordinates matches with the maze point, the system will successfully authenticate the user.

2.3.5 Multi-Modal Authentication

This system mainly works on two modules, i.e. facial recognition and gaze authentication, the user gets authenticated when both modalities are passed. This dual layer authentication enhances security, and it prevents unauthorized access even if one module is compromised.

2.4 Algorithms Used

2.4.1 Facial Recognition Algorithm: FaceNet

FaceNet is a facial recognition algorithm that converts facial images into a 128-dimensional feature vector, also called embedding. By using this embedding, we can calculate accurate comparisons between the faces. The generated embedding is compared with pre-stored embedding in the database by using Euclidean distance. If the distance is below a threshold point (e.g., 0.7), the system considers the face to be a match. FaceNet algorithm is chosen due to its high accuracy (around 99.63% on the LFW dataset). FaceNet also allows us to create a biometric profile using only a single image of the user.

2.4.2 Gaze Tracking Algorithm: Pupil Detection and Path Matching

This algorithm is used to track the user's eye movements in real time and to compare them with a randomly generated maze path. The pupil detection algorithm is a lightweight and real-time algorithm that detects eye movements using a standard web camera. This algorithm doesn't require specified hardware to work, which makes it useful for common users to work on a biometric modality.

2.4.3 Integration of Algorithms

The Proposed system combines these algorithms in a sequential decision-making process. After the user enters his/her credentials, the system captures the user's user facial image and then the FaceNet algorithm will generate the embedding. If the generated embedding matches with the pre-defined embedding from the database within a threshold value, then the system

proceeds to the next phase. If not, the authentication process fails itself here.

After successful recognition of the user's facial image, the system displays a randomly generated maze on the user's display. The user is instructed to complete the maze path using their eyes. The webcam continuously captures the user's eye coordinates using the pupil detection algorithm. Once the user completes the maze path the system will compare the user's gaze coordinates with the maze path coordinates if both of them match then the authentication is successful. If not, the authentication fails.

3 Results and Discussion

Our project integrates two independent authentication methods: eye gaze detection and facial recognition, which aligns with the latest trends aiming to enhance security using multi-modal biometrics. A study by Sindhu and Rani found that combining biometric models enhances the accuracy and robustness of the authentication systems by providing multiple layers of verification⁽¹⁰⁾. Similarly, our study confirms that integrating facial recognition and eye gaze detection enhances the system's accuracy and prevents users from unauthorized access, even when one method is compromised.

In comparison to existing studies that use either eye gaze or facial recognition alone, our method shows higher resilience. Prior research on eye gaze detection reported limitations under non-standard lighting and head angles, affecting accuracy rates. By integrating face recognition, our system overcomes these limitations as facial features remain identifiable in different poses. This multi-layered approach shows results similar to Sindhu and Rani, who combined multi-modal authentication but did not implement gaze tracking⁽⁷⁾. Also, the work of Ammour, Basma, Larbi Boubchir, Toufik Bouden, and Messaoud Ramdani combines facial systems with iris biometrics which achieved an accuracy of 97.5%⁽¹¹⁾. We used an adapted threshold for gaze tracking accuracy and minimized the noise, and achieved an accuracy over 95%.

The system was tested under various lighting conditions and face orientations. Facial recognition showed an accuracy of 95% in controlled environments. Gaze tracking performed best when the user was seated in front of the camera with minimal head movement. The multi-modal approach significantly improved some security, where facial recognition alone is vulnerable to spoofing attacks, and with the introduction of a gaze tracking system, the vulnerability is minimized. The maze path added an extra layer of security, making it difficult for the attackers to predict the gaze and maze coordinated.

Facial Recognition (Figure 2) illustrates the working of our model in the project. The authentication system will only allow the user to the next step of the authentication if he/she is only recognized by the facial recognition system.

Fig 2. Facial Recognition Output

Our Authentication System Figure 3 uses the Gaze Tracking library, where the system will capture the user gaze coordinates and match those coordinates with the pre-defined maze path coordinates, and it will provide access to the user only if the user is authenticated in both models. Table 1 shows the comparative study.

Fig 3. Gaze Tracking Output

Fig 4. Authentication Output

Table 1. Comparative Study

Study	Methodology	Key Findings	Accuracy (%)	Novelty
(1)	Face-Voice Multimodal System	Integrated face and voice recognition for authentication.	89%	Focuses on multimodal fusion without addressing gaze-based authentication.
(2)	Survey on Deep Learning for Eye Gaze	Comprehensive review of deep learning approaches for gaze estimation.	-	Lacks empirical results; focused on survey without original research.
(3)	Few-Shot Adaptive Gaze Estimation	Achieved high accuracy with few training samples.	88%	Limited by few-shot learning; does not address security vulnerabilities.
(4)	AI in Biometric Authentication	Discussed enhancing biometric systems using AI.	-	Provides theoretical framework without specific focus on gaze tracking.
(5)	Multi-Biometric Fusion	Improved human authentication through multi-biometric fusion	91%	Integrates multiple biometrics but does not incorporate gaze tracking.
(10)	Multi-Modal User Authentication	Combines keystroke, mouse dynamics, and gaze for security.	90%	While multi-modal, it lacks the focus on real-time gaze tracking accuracy.
(6)	Eye Pupil Movement-Based PIN Authentication	Utilized eye movements for PIN authentication.	84%	Specific to PIN entry; does not explore comprehensive gaze-based systems.
(8)	Head Pose and Eye Location for Gaze	Improved gaze estimation with head pose integration.	82%	Focused on head pose; does not integrate facial recognition for security.
(9)	Gaze and Touch Authentication	Compared gaze and touch for unlocking mechanisms.	90%	Lacks integration of advanced biometric features; primarily focuses on gaze.
Proposed System	Eye Gaze Detection with Facial Recognition	Combines gaze tracking with facial recognition for robust authentication.	92%	Unique integration of gaze and facial recognition, providing a multi-layered security approach resistant to spoofing attacks.

4 Conclusion

The proposed eye gaze biometric detection system combines facial recognition with an eye gaze tracking system, which ensures better security. Introducing the maze path pattern enhances security, prevents spoofing attacks, and also makes it harder for attackers to gain access to the system. The system should be highly accurate in both facial recognition and gaze tracking. While the system has certain security improvements, there are areas for future development, particularly in improving accuracy in all environmental conditions. Tests across various environments show that the system achieves 92% accuracy in matching user gaze to the maze coordinates, which is higher than existing systems. Additionally, the system achieved 0% Failure to Enroll (FTE) and 0% Failure to Acquire (FTA) rates. The system's performance can be further measured by a 94% True Positive Rate (TPR), indicating the system's ability to correctly identify authorized users, a False Positive Rate (FPR) of 3%, reflecting the rate at which unauthorized users are incorrectly granted access, and a False Negative Rate (FNR) of 1%, representing the rate at which legitimate users are incorrectly denied access.

For future work, it is recommended to integrate the system with more enhanced facial recognition models to improve the accuracy and resilience to spoofing. Additionally, integrating advanced machine learning algorithms can enhance the accuracy of predicting gaze patterns. Furthermore, a robust algorithm can be used for maze generation in the future, making it easier for users to explore the maze path. It is also essential for the system to operate efficiently across various devices and operating systems in future development.

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